

Kinetic study of electron transfer reaction between bis-acetylacetonatodiaquomanganese(III) perchlorate and thiosulfate, and investigation of factors influencing the electron transfer process

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Bisacetylacetonatodiaquomanganese(III) complex has been prepared in perchloric acid medium. Kinetic order of the reduction of this complex with thiosulfate is established. The reaction follows first order kinetics in complex, fractional order in both thiosulfate and $[H^+]$. The redox mechanism has been explained and the rate law derived. Activation parameters are computed and an outer-sphere mechanism is suggested for the reaction.

Several investigations have been recently reported which involve electron transfer reactions in aqueous solutions¹. Manganese(III) forms a variety of complexes with different organic and inorganic ligands². The majority of Mn^{III} complexes are high-spin and octahedral in nature. A few low-spin octahedral complexes, such as hexacyanomanganese(III) ion, are known³. High-spin Mn^{III} complexes result from the possibility that they might be distorted due to Jahn-Teller effect⁴. Bisacetylacetonatodiaquomanganese(III) complex used in the present study has a high solubility in aqueous solution and is stable in the pH range 2–5 in presence of 0.025 M acetylacetone. At higher pH values, bisacetylacetonatodiaquomanganese(III) ion acts as a weak acid having pK_h value⁵ of 7.3 and gets dissociated according to the equation,

As the pH approaches pK_h value, the solution forms turbidity and thus reaction rate is not observable in this pH range.

Results and discussion

The redox reaction was carried out under the pseudo-first order condition having $[S_2O_3^{2-}] \gg [complex]$ and data was collected using initial rate method by plotting the initial rates vs initial concentrations of reactants. The plots of initial rate vs initial concentration of complex at constant thiosulfate were found to be straight-line passing through the origin indicating that reaction is first order in complex as shown in Table 1. The k_{obs} values were calculated from the slopes of above plots.

Table 1 Kinetic rate data for pseudo first order rate constant between the reaction of $[Mn(acac)_2(H_2O)_2]$ and $[S_2O_3^{2-}]$

NaClO₄ = 0.5 M, λ_{max} = 298 nm, pH = 3.0, temp = 30^o
 $\epsilon = 90 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$

Set no	Initial [complex] $\times 10^5 \text{ M}$	Initial $[S_2O_3^{2-}] \times 10^4 \text{ M}$	Initial rate $\text{M s}^{-1} \times 10^4$	$k_{obs} \text{ s}^{-1}$ Expt	$k_{obs} \text{ s}^{-1}$ Recalc
1	8.33	11.66	7.35	8.9	9.16
	1.7	11.66	1.69		
	11.7	11.66	10.02		
	15	11.66	13.08		
2	8.33	16.66	11.99	13.3	12.64
	1.7	16.66	2.71		
	11.7	16.66	15.5		
	15	16.66	19.39		
3	8.33	25.0	14.07	18.5	19.27
	1.7	25.0	2.78		
	11.7	25.0	11.77		
	15.0	25.0	22.17		

Effect of thiosulfate on rate

At constant complex concentration (0.0005 M) and varying thiosulfate concentration (0.007, 0.01, 0.015 M), different sets of experiments were performed and graphs of initial rate vs initial concentration of thiosulfate were plotted which show that there is no change in the initial rate when the initial concentration of the thiosulfate is varied in one set of experiment. The results were found to be dependent upon the ratio of the concentration of the two reactants, thiosulfate and the complex. Thus there is no change in initial rate when initial concentration of thiosulfate is varied in each set of the experiments. However, initial rate gets increased in these experiments as the ratios of concen-

trations of thiosulfate complex were increased, as shown in Table 2, indicating the fractional order dependence in thiosulfate concentration. Double-reciprocal plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[S_2O_3^{2-}]$, keeping all remaining conditions constant, was found to be straight line with positive slope and intercept on y-axis and the data are given in Table 3 (eqn. 8).

Table 2. Dependence of initial rate on $[S_2O_3^{2-}]$

NaClO ₄ = 0.5 M, pH = 3.0, temp. = 30°					
Set. no.	Initial [complex] × 10 ⁵ M	Initial $[S_2O_3^{2-}]$ × 10 ⁴ M	Initial rate M s ⁻¹ × 10 ⁴	Stock [complex] M	Stock $[S_2O_3^{2-}]$ M
1	8.33	4.7	7.33		
	8.33	7.0	7.34	0.0005	0.007
	8.33	9.33	7.35		
	8.33	11.7	7.35		
2	8.33	6.7	12.0		
	8.33	10.0	12.0	0.0005	0.01
	8.33	13.3	12.1		
	8.33	16.6	11.97		
3	8.33	10.1	14.07		
	8.33	15.0	13.96	0.0005	0.015
	8.33	20.0	14.07		
	8.33	25.0	14.07		

Table 3. Dependence of k_{obs} on $[S_2O_3^{2-}]$

NaClO ₄ = 0.5 M, pH = 3.0, Temp. = 30°			
k_{obs}	$[S_2O_3^{2-}]$ × 10 ⁴ M	$1/k_{\text{obs}}$	$1/[S_2O_3^{2-}]$ M ⁻¹
8.9	11.66	0.112	857.63
13.3	16.66	0.075	600.24
18.5	25.0	0.054	400.00
25	33.32	0.040	300.12

Effect of $[H^+]$ on k_{obs} :

To study the effect of $[H^+]$ on rate, kinetic runs were carried out using HClO₄ to vary the $[H^+]$. NaClO₄ was used to maintain constant ionic strength of 0.5 M. The remaining conditions were kept unaltered. It was observed that the rate is independent of $[H^+]$ in the pH range 2.5–5.0 and above pH 5 the rate decreased (Table 4). This decrease in the rate suggests a fractional order kinetics. Plot of k_{obs} vs $[H^+]$ was found to be curved while that of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[H^+]$ was straight line with positive slope (eqn. 20). This decrease of rate above pH 5 may be due to hydrolysis of complex into its hydroxy product. It is evident that the complex acts as a weak acid at high pH values, when $\text{pH} \geq \text{p}K_{\text{H}}$.

Table 4. Dependence of k_{obs} on $[H^+]$

$[Mn(acac)_2(H_2O)_2] = 0.0005 M, [S_2O_3^{2-}] = 0.015 M, NaClO_4 = 0.5 M, \text{temp.} = 30^\circ$			
k_{obs} s	$[H^+]$ × 10 ⁴ M	$1/k_{\text{obs}}$ s	$1/[H^+]$ × 10 ⁻⁴
18.5	100	0.054	0.01
18.5	32	0.054	0.032
18.5	10	0.054	0.1
18.5	3.2	0.054	0.313
18.4 ^a	1	0.054	1
18.4	0.1	0.054	10
17.6	0.01	0.057	100
17.1	0.0063	0.058	158
16.41	0.004	0.061	250
15.42	0.0025	0.065	400

Effect of ionic strength on k_{obs} :

The effect of ionic strength (*I*) on the rate of reaction was investigated by varying concentration of NaClO₄ in the medium, keeping all other conditions constant, where complex and thiosulfate concentrations were fixed at 0.001 M and 0.01 M, respectively. The results are summarized in Table 5. The plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $I^{1/2}$ was linear with a negative slope of -1.7, which shows that the reactants bear the opposite charges. As the complex carries a charge of +1 and thiosulfate has -2 charge, the charge of the resulting product is suggested to be -2. The results obtained using Debye-Hückel limiting law are consistent with this value.

Table 5. Dependence of k_{obs} on ionic strength (NaClO₄)

$[Mn(acac)_2(H_2O)_2] = 0.001 M, [S_2O_3^{2-}] = 0.01 M, \text{temp.} = 30^\circ$			
<i>I</i> (NaClO ₄)	<i>I</i> ^{1/2}	k_{obs}	$\log k_{\text{obs}}$
0.025	0.158	100	2.0
0.05	0.223	75	1.88
0.075	0.274	61	1.78
0.1	0.316	53	1.72
0.2	0.447	31	1.49
0.5	0.707	11	1.04
0.8	0.894	5.3	0.72
1	1	3.6	0.57

Effect of temperature on k_{obs} :

At pH 3.0, complex concentration of 0.0005 M, thiosulfate concentration of 0.0015 M and ionic strength of 0.5 M (NaClO₄), the temperature dependence of k_{obs} was studied in the range of 30–45°. The results are given in Table 6 and the plot of $\ln (k_{\text{obs}}/T)$ vs $1/T$ is linear with a slope of -1527 K and intercept 2.25. From slope and intercept activation parameters $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ were calculated to be 12.69 kJ mol⁻¹ and -179 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹, respectively.

Table 6. Dependence of k_{obs} on temperature

[Mn(acac)₂(H₂O)₂][‡] = 0.0005 M, [S₂O₃²⁻] = 0.015 M, NaClO₄ = 0.5 M, pH = 3.0

T (K)	k_{obs}	ln k_{obs}	1/T × 10 ³	ln (k_{obs}/T)
303	18.5	2.92	3.30	-2.79
308	20.51	3.02	3.25	-2.71
313	22.66	3.12	3.19	-2.63
318	24.96	3.22	3.14	-2.54
323	27.40	3.31	3.09	-2.47

Mechanism :

Stoichiometry of the reaction is given as

The mechanism involves reactions (2,3) with the formation of ion-pair between complex and thiosulfate, which is reversible and gets dissociated into products.

The rate of reaction is given as

$$\text{Rate} = - d[\text{Mn(acac)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{\ddagger}]/dt = k_1[\text{Mn(acac)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)^-] \quad (4)$$

Assuming that the intermediate species [Mn(acac)₂(H₂O)₂(S₂O₃)⁻] forms quickly, equilibrium constant for the formation of ion-pair is represented as

$$K_{ip} = \frac{[\text{Mn(acac)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)^-]}{[\text{Mn(acac)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{\ddagger}][\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]} \quad (5)$$

where,

$$[\text{Mn(acac)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{\ddagger}] = \frac{[\text{Mn(acac)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)^-]}{[\text{Mn(acac)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{\ddagger}] - [\text{Mn(acac)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)^-]}$$

Substituting [Mn(acac)₂(H₂O)₂][‡] in eqn. (5) and rearranging,

$$[\text{Mn(acac)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)^-] = \frac{K_{ip}[\text{Mn(acac)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{\ddagger}][\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]}{1 + K_{ip}[\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]}$$

Substituting for [Mn(acac)₂(H₂O)₂(S₂O₃)⁻] in eqn. (4), we have

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_1 K_{ip} [\text{Mn(acac)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{\ddagger}][\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]}{1 + K_{ip}[\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]} \quad (6)$$

As pseudo-first order conditions prevail, first order rate constant is taken as

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_1 K_{ip} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]}{1 + K_{ip}[\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]} \quad (7)$$

Taking reciprocals on both sides, eqn. (7) becomes

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{1}{k_1 K_{ip} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]} + \frac{1}{k_1} \quad (8)$$

Plot of 1/ k_{obs} vs 1/[S₂O₃²⁻] is linear in accordance with rate eqn. (8). The constants K_{ip} and k_1 were calculated from slope (1/ $k_1 K_{ip}$ = 0.000125) and intercept (1/ k_1 = 0.00175) and were found to be 14.01 M⁻¹ and 571.43 s⁻¹, respectively. A good agreement was found between the recalculated rate constants from eqn. (7) and experimental rate constants. This confirms the proposed mechanism and the reaction proceeds through an outer-sphere mechanism due to the formation of ion-pair.

Introducing the acid dissociation equilibrium of [Mn(acac)₂(H₂O)₂][‡] into rate equation.

The mass balance equation for Mn^{III} at equilibrium is

$$[\text{Mn}^{III}]_T = [\text{Mn(acac)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{\ddagger}] + [\text{Mn(acac)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})]$$

Substituting for [Mn(acac)₂(H₂O)(OH)] in eqn. (9) gives

$$[\text{Mn(acac)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{\ddagger}] = \frac{[\text{Mn}^{III}]_T [\text{H}^+]}{K_h + [\text{H}^+]}$$

Eqn. (6) becomes

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_1 K_{ip} [\text{Mn}^{III}]_T [\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}] [\text{H}^+]}{(1 + K_{ip}[\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}])([\text{H}^+] + K_h)} \quad (10)$$

or

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_1 K_{ip} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}] [\text{Mn}^{III}]_T}{(1 + K_{ip}[\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]) \left(\frac{1 + K_h}{[\text{H}^+]} \right)} \quad (11)$$

and

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_1 K_{ip} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}] [\text{H}^+]}{(1 + K_{ip}[\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}])([\text{H}^+] + K_h)} \quad (12)$$

=

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_1 K_{ip} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]}{(1 + K_{ip}[\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]) \left(\frac{1 + K_h}{[\text{H}^+]} \right)} \quad (13)$$

Eqn. (10) can be solved in two parts,

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$$k_{\text{obs}} = kk' \quad (14)$$

where,

$$k = \frac{k_1 K_{\text{ip}} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]}{1 + K_{\text{ip}} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]} \quad (15)$$

$$k' = \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{([\text{H}^+] + K_{\text{h}})} \quad (16)$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_1 K_{\text{ip}} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}] k'}{1 + K_{\text{ip}} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]} \quad (17)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{k_1 K_{\text{ip}} k' [\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]} + \frac{1}{k_1 k'} \quad (18)$$

From the plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]$, k' was evaluated and found to agree to the value of k' calculated through eqn (16),

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{[\text{H}^+]k}{([\text{H}^+] + K_{\text{h}})} \quad (19)$$

Taking reciprocals on both sides, eqn. (19) becomes

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{k} + \frac{K_{\text{h}}}{k[\text{H}^+]} \quad (20)$$

According to this equation, plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/\text{H}^+$ must be straight line if all other factors were kept constant. k calculated from the intercept of this plot is in agreement with that determined through eqns. (7) and (15). Further, K_{h} (5.55×10^{-8}) calculated from the slope of this plot tallied with the literature value (5×10^{-8})⁵.

Experimental

All chemicals were of AnalaR grade. Sodium thiosulfate was standardized iodometrically⁶. Complex $[\text{Mn}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ was prepared as described earlier⁵.

Absorption spectra were recorded at 298 nm by using a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer and molar extinction coefficient was found to be $90 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Mn^{III} was analyzed potentiometrically. In this technique, trisacetylacetonatodiaquomanganese(III) complex, $[\text{Mn}(\text{acac})_3]$, was reduced by L-ascorbic acid and potential difference between the indicator electrode (bright platinum

electrode) and reference electrode (Saturated Calomel Electrode) was read with the aid of a potentiometer (Kent EIL 7020). Amount of Mn^{III} was calculated from the equivalence point by using second derivative plot of $\Delta^2 E / \Delta v^2$ as a function of mean of V_{avg} (average volume). Analysis of the above complex gave Mn 17.1% (calcd. 15.6%).

Kinetic measurements : The kinetic study of the reduction of $[\text{Mn}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ by $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]$ was carried out under the pseudo-first order conditions having $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}] \gg [\text{complex}]$. Different combinations of both complex and reductant (sodium thiosulfate) were prepared by taking constant concentration of the complex (0.0005 M) and varying the concentration of the reductant (0.007, 0.01, 0.015, 0.02, 0.025 M). Perchloric acid was used as a source of hydrogen ion for pH 3.0, and all solutions were adjusted to an ionic strength (I) of 0.5 mol dm^{-3} (NaClO_4). Various ratios of complex and thiosulfate solutions were mixed in a 1-cm quartz cells to a total volume of 3 ml. The concentrations of components of the reaction mixture were predetermined and they were kept at desired temperatures in a thermostat. The optical density was monitored spectrophotometrically as a function of time of each set of reaction mixture at 298 nm. A Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer, an Orion pH meter and a Kent EIL 7020 potentiometer were used.

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